

A NEW APPROACH CONCERNING MECHANICAL BEHAVIOUR OF MULTIDIRECTIONAL COMPOSITE STRIPS

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SUMMARY

The new approach is based on the assumption of a displacement field with all deformation modes of the strip, including edgewise bending. Moreover, null stresses are assumed along the width of the strip. The new approach can be applied to the analysis of tensile and flexure tests of multidirectional laminates.

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INTRODUCTION

In tensile and flexure tests, if the axes of the specimen are not principal directions of orthotropy, forces and moments appear due to coupling effects [1-4]. Figure 1(a) shows the forces and moments in a tensile test when P force is applied. Figure 1(b) shows the support reactions and the applied force P in a three-point bending test. In this case, it is assumed that the contact between the specimen and supports is located at the four corners.

Figure 1. Forces and moments in tensile and flexure tests.

Since specimens used in mechanical tests have strip geometry, the objective of the present work is to show the main aspects of a new approach named Laminated Strip Theory (LST) that allows to determine redundant unknowns that appear in Figure 1. As a consequence, stresses and displacements caused by coupling effects can be included in the interpretation of results.

DISPLACEMENT FIELD

It is assumed that displacement field is given by the superposition of two fields, corresponding to flatwise and edgewise configurations, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} u(x, y, z) &= u_0(x) + z\varphi(x, y) + y\psi(x) \\ v(x, y, z) &= v_1(x) + y\eta(x) + (z - z_c)\theta(x) \\ w(x, y, z) &= w_0(x) - y\theta(x) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

φ and ψ are rotated angles of the cross section with respect to y and z axes, respectively. θ is twisting angle and η is the mean strain in y direction. z_c is the position of the shear centre, located at z axis.

STRAIN FIELD

Using primes to denote derivatives with respect to x of functions that only depend on x , normal strain in the longitudinal direction of the strip ε_x and shear strain in the plane xy , $\gamma_{xy} = \gamma_s$ are obtained from Eq.(1), being:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \gamma_s \end{Bmatrix} &= \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \gamma_s^0 \end{Bmatrix} + y \begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_z \\ \eta' \end{Bmatrix} + z \begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_s \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^1 \\ \gamma_s^1 \end{Bmatrix} + z \begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_s \end{Bmatrix} \\ \varepsilon_x^0 &= u_0' \quad \gamma_s^0 = v_1' + \psi - z_c \theta' \\ \varepsilon_x^1 &= \varepsilon_x^0 + y \kappa_z \quad \gamma_s^1 = \gamma_s^0 + y \eta' \\ \kappa_x &= \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} \quad \kappa_s = \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial y} + \theta' \quad \kappa_z = \psi' \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The mean value along the thickness of the out-of-plane shear strain $\bar{\gamma}_z$ is:

$$\bar{\gamma}_z(x, y) = \varphi(x, y) + w_0' - y\theta' \quad (3)$$

$\bar{\gamma}_z$ and φ are decomposed in a symmetric and a skew-symmetric part. It is assumed that symmetric part is related to bending and skew-symmetric part is related to twisting. Furthermore, it is assumed that terms related to bending $\bar{\gamma}_z^b$ and φ^b are uniform along

the width of the strip and that φ' does not depend on x . Then, bending and twisting curvatures of Eq.(2) are given by:

$$\begin{aligned}\kappa_x &= \frac{\partial \varphi^b}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \bar{\gamma}_z^b}{\partial x} - w_0'' \\ \kappa_s &= \frac{\partial \varphi^t}{\partial y} + \theta' = \frac{\partial \bar{\gamma}_z^t}{\partial y} + 2\theta'\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

Otherwise, the mean value of γ_s along the thickness is γ_s^0 . The mean value in the whole section $\bar{\gamma}_s$ is:

$$\bar{\gamma}_s(x) = \psi + v_1' - z_c \theta' \quad (5)$$

STRESS-STRAIN RELATION

It is assumed that $\sigma_y = 0$ and $\tau_{yz} = 0$. Stress-strain relation in the laminate plane is:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x \\ \gamma_s \end{Bmatrix} - \begin{Bmatrix} e_x \\ e_s \end{Bmatrix}_k = \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^* \\ \gamma_s^* \end{Bmatrix}_k = \begin{bmatrix} S_{xx} & S_{xs} \\ S_{xs} & S_{ss} \end{bmatrix}_k \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \tau_s \end{Bmatrix}_k \quad (6)$$

Higrothermal strains being: $e_i = \alpha_i \Delta T + \beta_i \Delta c$. Inverting Eq.(6), in-plane stresses are:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \tau_s \end{Bmatrix}_k = \begin{bmatrix} q_{xx} & q_{xs} \\ q_{xs} & q_{ss} \end{bmatrix}_k \left(\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^1 \\ \gamma_s^1 \end{Bmatrix} + z \begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_x \\ \kappa_s \end{Bmatrix} - \begin{Bmatrix} e_x \\ e_s \end{Bmatrix}_k \right) \text{ where } \begin{bmatrix} q_{xx} & q_{xs} \\ q_{xs} & q_{ss} \end{bmatrix}_k = \begin{bmatrix} S_{xx} & S_{xs} \\ S_{xs} & S_{ss} \end{bmatrix}_k^{-1} \quad (7)$$

The relation between stiffness coefficients q_{ij} and Q_{ij} is:

$$q_{xx} = Q_{xx} - \frac{Q_{xy}^2}{Q_{yy}} \quad q_{xs} = Q_{xs} - \frac{Q_{xy}Q_{ys}}{Q_{yy}} \quad q_{ss} = Q_{ss} - \frac{Q_{ys}^2}{Q_{yy}} \quad (8)$$

Out-of-plane stress-strain relation is given by $\gamma_{zx} = S_{55}^1 \tau_{zx}$. Nevertheless, mean values of strain and stress along the thickness will be considered. Equivalent compliances S_z^b and S_z^t corresponding to bending and twisting will be calculated based on strain energy principles [5,6].

FORCES AND MOMENTS PER UNIT LENGTH

Forces and moments per unit length are defined in the same manner than in Classical Laminated Plates Theory (CLPT). Relating forces and moments per unit length with stresses, it results that:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{Bmatrix} n_x \\ n_s \\ m_x \\ m_s \end{Bmatrix} &= \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \tau_s \end{Bmatrix}_k dz \Rightarrow \{n\} = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \{\sigma\}_k dz \\ \begin{Bmatrix} m_x \\ m_s \end{Bmatrix} &= \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_x \\ \tau_s \end{Bmatrix}_k z dz \Rightarrow \{m\} = \sum_{k=1}^n \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \{\sigma\}_k z dz \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Replacing stresses from Eq.(7) and solving integrals of Eq.(9):

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{Bmatrix} n_x \\ n_s \\ m_x \\ m_s \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} n_x^{HT} \\ n_s^{HT} \\ m_x^{HT} \\ m_s^{HT} \end{Bmatrix} &= \begin{Bmatrix} n_x^* \\ n_s^* \\ m_x^* \\ m_s^* \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} a_{xx} & a_{xs} & b_{xx} & b_{xs} \\ a_{xs} & a_{ss} & b_{xs} & b_{ss} \\ b_{xx} & b_{xs} & d_{xx} & d_{xs} \\ b_{xs} & b_{ss} & d_{xs} & d_{ss} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^1 \\ \gamma_s^1 \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_s \end{Bmatrix} \\ a_{ij} &= \sum_{k=1}^n q_{ij}^k (z_k - z_{k-1}) \quad b_{ij} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n q_{ij}^k (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2) \quad d_{ij} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_{k=1}^n q_{ij}^k (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3) \\ n_i^{HT} &= \sum_{k=1}^n (q_{ix}^k e_x + q_{is}^k e_s) (z_k - z_{k-1}) \quad m_i^{HT} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n (q_{ix}^k e_x + q_{is}^k e_s) (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The inverted relation of Eq.(10) is:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^1 \\ \gamma_s^1 \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_s \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_{xx} & f_{xs} & g_{xx} & g_{xs} \\ f_{xs} & f_{ss} & g_{sx} & g_{ss} \\ g_{xx} & g_{sx} & h_{xx} & h_{xs} \\ g_{xs} & g_{ss} & h_{xs} & h_{ss} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} n_x^* \\ n_s^* \\ m_x^* \\ m_s^* \end{Bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

Thermal stresses of AS4/3501-6 carbon/epoxy at room temperature are considered as example. The temperature variation is -155 °C . The laminate configuration is [45₆/-45₆], and ply thickness is supposed to be 0.125 mm. Figure 2 shows differences between thermal normal stresses obtained by CLPT and LST, being twice as great in the case of CLPT.

Figure 2. Thermal normal stresses of [45₆/-45₆] configuration. (a) LST; (b) CLPT.

FORCES AND MOMENTS OF THE CROSS SECTION

Forces and moments in the whole section N_x , N_s , M_x and M_s are obtained after integrating Eq.(11) along the width of the strip, resulting in:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_x^0 \\ \bar{\gamma}_s \\ \kappa_x \\ \kappa_s^1 \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} f_{xx} & f_{xs} & g_{xx} & g_{xs} \\ f_{xs} & f_{ss}^1 & g_{sx} & g_{ss} \\ g_{xx} & g_{sx} & h_{xx} & h_{xs} \\ g_{xs} & g_{ss} & h_{xs} & h_{ss} \end{bmatrix} \frac{1}{b} \begin{Bmatrix} N_x^* \\ N_s^* \\ M_x^* \\ M_s^* \end{Bmatrix} \quad \text{where } \kappa_s^1 = 2\theta' + \frac{\bar{\gamma}_z^t(b_1)}{b_1} \quad (12)$$

Considering that hygrothermal effects are uniform, equivalent forces and moments of the cross section are: $N_i^{HT} = bn_i^{HT}$ $M_i^{HT} = bm_i^{HT}$ being b the width of the strip and $b_1 = \frac{b}{2}$. Since mean shear stress is used, f_{ss} is changed to f_{ss}^1 in Eq.(12). The modified coefficient will be calculated according to energy principles. Multiplying by y the first equation of Eq.(10) and integrating it results:

$$M_z = \frac{b^3}{12} (a_{xx}\kappa_z + a_{xs}\eta') \quad (13)$$

Multiplying by y the first and second equations of Eq.(11) and integrating it results:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \kappa_z \\ \eta' \end{Bmatrix} = \frac{12}{b^3} \begin{bmatrix} f_{xx} & f_{xs} \\ f_{xs} & f_{ss} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} M_z \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

V_z is the resultant force of the symmetric part of the v_z , named v_z^b . Knowing the forces and moments in the cross sections strains and curvatures can be obtained. Nevertheless, the term $\bar{\gamma}_z^l(b_1)$ is not known.

EDGEWISE CONFIGURATION

Distribution of n_s shear forces

It is supposed that the strip is acted on by M_z and N_s . The following equilibrium equation must be satisfied:

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_x^k}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_s^k}{\partial y} = 0 \quad (15)$$

According to Eq.(7) normal stress at ply k is:

$$\sigma_x^k = q_{xx}^k (\varepsilon_x^0 + z\kappa_x + y\kappa_z) + q_{xs}^k (\gamma_s^0 + y\eta' + z\kappa_s) \quad (16)$$

It is assumed that η' do not depend on x , that is $\eta'' = 0$. In order to include this assumption, Eq.(14) is considered. Taking into account that the unique term of Eq.(16) that depend on x is κ_z , and $\tau_s(b_1) = 0$, after integrating Eq.(15) it results that:

$$\tau_s^k = \frac{6}{a_{xx} b^3} q_{xx}^k N_s \left(\frac{b^2}{4} - y^2 \right) \quad (17)$$

Integrating Eq.(17) with respect to z it results that:

$$n_s = \frac{6}{b^3} N_s \left(\frac{b^2}{4} - y^2 \right) \quad (18)$$

Shear center is the application point of the resultant of τ_s shear stresses. Due to the symmetry with respect to z , it is supposed that it is at that axis. In order to calculate the distance z_C , the theorem of Varignon is applied. Considering Eq.(17) and (18) it results:

$$n_s z_C = \int_{-h_1}^{h_1} \tau_s z dz \Rightarrow z_C = \frac{b_{xx}}{a_{xx}} \quad (19)$$

Equivalent shear compliance

The direct relation between $\bar{\gamma}_s$ and n_s is given by coefficient f_{ss} . This coefficient is modified in order to include the effect of parabolic distribution of n_s . It is supposed that the work performed by forces n_s and strains γ_s^1 in an element of length dx is the same that the work performed by the force N_s and the mean strain $\bar{\gamma}_s$. That is:

$$\frac{1}{2} N_s \bar{\gamma}_s dx = \frac{1}{2} \int_{-b_1}^{b_1} n_s \gamma_s^1 dy dx \Rightarrow f_{ss}^1 = \frac{6}{5} f_{ss} \quad (20)$$

FLATWISE CONFIGURATION: N_x , M_x AND V_z

Distribution of n_x , m_x and v_z

It is assumed that normal force n_x bending moment m_y and shear force v_z^b are applied uniformly along the width of the beam.

Interlaminar shear stresses

The following equilibrium equation must be satisfied:

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_x^k}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zx}^k}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (21)$$

Introducing normal stresses of Eq.(7) in Eq.(21) it results that:

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{zx}^k(z) &= v_z^b \left[- \left(A_g^k z + A_h^k \frac{z^2}{2} \right) + B_k \right] \\ A_g^k &= q_{xx}^k g_{xx} + q_{xs}^k g_{sx} \quad A_h^k = q_{xx}^k h_{xx} + q_{xs}^k h_{xs} \\ B_k &= A_g^1 z_0 + A_h^1 \frac{z_0^2}{2} + \sum_{i=2}^k \left[\left(A_g^i - A_g^{i-1} \right) z_{i-1} + \left(A_h^i - A_h^{i-1} \right) \frac{z_{i-1}^2}{2} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

Equivalent shear compliance

Strain energy corresponding to an elemeng of length dx , width dy and thickness h is calculated in two ways: considering the actual distribution of stresses and considering mean values, as follows

$$\begin{aligned} U_b &= \left(\frac{1}{2} \int_{-h_1}^{h_1} \tau_{zx} \gamma_{zx} dz \right) dx dy = \left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n S_{55}^{tk} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \tau_{zx}^2 dz \right) dx dy \\ U_b &= \left(\frac{1}{2} v_z^b \bar{\gamma}_z^b \right) dx dy = \left(\frac{1}{2h} S_z^b (v_z^b)^2 \right) dx dy \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

Introducing interlaminar stresses of Eq.(22) in Eq.(23) it results

$$S_z^b = h \sum_{k=1}^n S_{55}^k \left\{ \begin{aligned} & \frac{(A_h^k)^2}{20} (z_k^5 - z_{k-1}^5) + \frac{A_g^k A_h^k}{4} (z_k^4 - z_{k-1}^4) + \frac{1}{3} [(A_g^k)^2 - A_h^k B_k] (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3) \\ & - B_k A_g^k (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2) + (B_k)^2 (z_k - z_{k-1}) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (24)$$

FLATWISE CONFIGURATION: TWISTING MOMENT

Distribution of m_s and v_z^t

Twisting moment per unit length m_s related to τ_s stresses, can be obtained from Eq.(10) and (11), being:

$$m_s = \frac{d_{ss}}{(1-A)} \kappa_s = d_{ss}^1 \kappa_s \quad \text{where } A = b_{xs} g_{xs} + b_{ss} g_{ss} + d_{xs} h_{xs} \quad (25)$$

Taking into account the equilibrium condition $\frac{\partial m_s}{\partial y} = v_z^t$ and κ_s given in Eq.(4), it results

$$\frac{\partial^2 \bar{\gamma}_z^t}{\partial y^2} - k^2 \bar{\gamma}_z^t = 0 \quad \text{where } k^2 = \frac{h}{S_z^t d_{ss}^1} \quad (26)$$

Integrating Eq.(26) and applying boundary conditions it results

$$\bar{\gamma}_z^t(y) = -\frac{2\theta'}{k \cosh \lambda} \sinh ky \quad m_s = d_{ss}^1 2\theta' \left(1 - \frac{\cosh ky}{\cosh \lambda} \right) \quad (27)$$

It is seen that the contribution of m_s and v_z^t in the twisting moment is the same, that is:

$$\begin{aligned} M_t &= M_s - \int_{-b_1}^{b_1} v_z^t y dy \\ M_s &= \int_{-b_1}^{b_1} m_s dy = \int_{-b_1}^{b_1} -v_z^t y dy = b d_{ss}^1 2\theta' (1 - \xi) \Rightarrow M_t = 2M_s \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Replacing the value of $\bar{\gamma}_z^t(b_1)$ from Eq.(27) in the second of Eq.(28) the derivative of the twisting angle is obtained, being:

$$2\theta' = \frac{\kappa_s^1}{1-\xi} \quad (29)$$

Where $\xi = \frac{\tanh \lambda}{\lambda}$. Since usually $b > 3h$ and then $\lambda \gg 1$, in a first approach it is assumed that $2\theta' = \kappa_s^1$.

Interlaminar shear stresses

Interlaminar stresses can be calculated in a similar way than in the bending case. The following equilibrium equation must be satisfied:

$$\frac{\partial \tau_{yz}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zx}}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (30)$$

Introducing shear stresses of Eq.(7) in Eq.(21) it results that

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{zx}^k(z) &= v_z^t \left[- \left(B_g^k (z_k - z_{k-1}) + B_h^k \frac{z^2}{2} \right) + C_k \right] \\ B_g^k &= q_{xs}^k g_{xs} + q_{ss}^k g_{ss} \quad B_h^k = q_{xs}^k h_{xs} + q_{ss}^k h_{ss} \\ C_k &= B_g^1 z_0 + B_h^1 \frac{z_0^2}{2} + \sum_{i=2}^k \left[(B_g^i - B_g^{i-1}) z_{i-1} + (B_h^i - B_h^{i-1}) \frac{z_{i-1}^2}{2} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

Equivalent shear compliance

In a similar manner than in bending case, strain energy is calculated in two ways: considering the actual distribution of stresses and considering mean values, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} U_t &= \left(\frac{1}{2} \int_{-h_1}^{h_1} \tau_{zx} \gamma_{zx} dz \right) dxdy = \left(\frac{1}{2} \sum_{k=1}^n S_{55}^{ik} \int_{z_{k-1}}^{z_k} \tau_{zx}^2 dz \right) dxdy \\ U_t &= \left(\frac{1}{2} v_z^t \gamma_z^t \right) dxdy = \left(\frac{1}{2h} S_z^t (v_z^t)^2 \right) dxdy \end{aligned} \quad (32)$$

Introducing interlaminar stresses of Eq.(31) in Eq.(32) it results

$$S_z^t = h \sum_{k=1}^n S_{55}^{ik} \left\{ \begin{aligned} &\left[\frac{(B_h^k)^2}{20} (z_k^5 - z_{k-1}^5) + \frac{B_g^k B_h^k}{4} (z_k^4 - z_{k-1}^4) + \frac{1}{3} \left[(B_g^k)^2 - B_h^k C_k \right] (z_k^3 - z_{k-1}^3) \right] \\ &- C_k B_g^k (z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2) + (C_k)^2 (z_k - z_{k-1}) \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (33)$$

APPLICATION TO TENSILE AND FLEXURE TESTS

Statically indetermined forces of Figure 1 can be determined by the following calculation process, taking into account boundary conditions:

1. $M_z \rightarrow \text{Eq.}(14) \psi' \rightarrow \psi$
2. Eq.(12) $\bar{\gamma}_s \rightarrow \text{Eq. (5)} v_1' \rightarrow v_1$
3. Eq.(12) $\kappa_x \rightarrow \text{Eq (4)} \varphi^b, \bar{\gamma}_z^b \rightarrow w_0' \rightarrow w_0$
4. Eq.(12) $\theta \rightarrow \theta$

Then, displacements and stresses can be determined in the general case of a multidirectional laminate including the effect of coupling forces and moments that appear in Figure 1. The results obtained by this approach in the case of unidirectional off-axis tensile and flexure tests agree with solutions given in references [2] and [3], respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

According to LST, reduced stiffness coefficients vary with respect to CLPT. Then, there are differences between stresses obtained by both approaches in the case of multidirectional laminates. Furthermore, redundant forces and moments that appear in mechanical tests induced by coupling effects can be determined by means of the displacement field of LST.

References

1. Pagano, N.J. and Halpin, J.C. (1968). Influence of End Constraint in the Testing of Anisotropic Bodies, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **2**: 19–31.
2. Mujika F, (2005). New considerations on the stress field in an off-axis tensile test, *Journal of composite materials*, **39** (21): 1909-1929.
3. Mujika F, Mondragon I, (2003). On the displacement field for unidirectional off-axis composites in 3-point flexure - Part 1: Analytical approach, *Journal of composite materials*, **37** (12): 1041-1066.
4. Mujika F, de Benito A, Mondragon I, (2003). On the displacement field for unidirectional off-axis composites in 3-point flexure - Part 2: Numerical and experimental results, *Journal of composite materials*, **37** (13): 1191-1217.
5. Berthelot, J.M. (1996). *Matériaux Composites, Comportement Mécanique et Analyse des Structures*, Masson, Paris.
6. Vasiliev, V.V. and Morozov E. V. (2007). *Advanced Mechanics of Composite Materials*, Elsevier, Amsterdam.